

Non-invasive Pin-less Halo Orthosis

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Abstract: A spinal orthotic device is an external apparatus applied to the body to limit the motion of, correct deformity in, reduce axial loading on, or improve the function of particular spinal segment of the body. HALO is a medical device used to stabilize the cervical spine after traumatic injuries to the neck or after spine surgery. The apparatus consists of a halo vest, stabilization bars, and a metal ring encircling the patient's head and fixated to the skull with multiple pins. The metal pins push up to the skull and not into it. This device is complex and it has an invasive procedure, so a concept of non-invasive HALO device have been designed. It's a pin less HALO system with the goal of providing cervical spine immobilization and control is similar to standard halo, but in a less invasive manner. The non- invasive halo system can be used in the management of a variety of cervical spine disorder.

Keyword: Non Invasive Halo, Cervical spine fractures, Torticollis, Pin –less, Spinal immobilization, Axial deloading, Turnbuckles, Custom made spinal orthotic device, Cervical disorders.

1. Introduction:

The head and neck are two examples of the perfect anatomical conjugation between form and function, mixed with a dash of complexity. The neck is resilient enough to sustain a five kilogram weight 24/7, yet sufficiently mobile to move it in several directions. On the other end, the head is durable enough to protect the fragile brain but intricately designed to facilitate the passage of the complex neurovascular network.

Surgical fixation of cervical spinal fractures in general, has gained popularity. Improved imaging techniques together with more reliable surgical tools have lowered the threshold for surgery, offering the patient a short-term solution for his fracture. Conservative measures, i.e. non-surgical tools, still have a role to play, either in the initial stage, either later on as an adjunct to surgery, or as the definitive treatment. The goal is to provide a stable and hopefully painless spine together with the best possible neurologic recovery. Pre-hospital care at the trauma site, followed by adequate evaluation at the emergency department, is critical. Transportation must be carried out on a spinal board, with the patient's neck immobilised by means of a collar, sandbags, and tape fixation. Clinical examination must be followed by a radiographic workup, consisting of appropriate radiographs, and CT scan allowing in assessing any fractures or dislocations. The type of fracture or dislocation, together with the neurologic status of the patient, will determine which therapeutic strategy seems most appropriate. Skeletal skull traction certainly still has a role to play in the initial phase, and is mainly indicated in cases of facet subluxation or dislocation, and in burst-type fractures, to stabilize and realign the cervical spine. Upper cervical fractures are also the candidates for skull traction, whereas traction is contraindicated for distractive injuries or patients with certain skull fractures.

Torticollis which is one of the postural deformity in the cervical region can also be managed by conservative treatment. Torticollis is a 3 dimensional deformity where cervical flexion occurs in the sagittal plane, lateral flexion in the frontal plane and rotation of head in the transverse plane. The custom made cervical orthotic device which are available are Fillauer Torticollis Orthosis, Static Rotation control Orthosis, Minerva Design, Cuirass Orthosis, Dynamic Torticollis Orthosis, Multi-adjustable post-operative Orthosis, Cephalo - cervico Thoracic dynamic splint, etc.

The above mentioned orthotic device does not provide the required immobilization and stability which is needed in the cervical fracture and the correction for the deformity is unachievable. So, HALO device is best suited spinal orthotics for this type of conditions. HALO ring is the component used in this device with halo vest is considered as a definitive treatment. In children, the use of multiple halo pins is recommended in order

to reduce pull-out force, increase stiffness, and allow for a lower torque applied to the pins. So our concept is to fabricate a pinless Halo system which makes it non-invasive and a painless procedures.

Methodology:

The orthosis can be fabricated in two methods:

1. By moulding directly over the patient's body.

The material used for fabrication of orthosis is LTTP. LTTP is strong and flexible at room temperature. It has a low melting point. So, it can be made soft using a hot water bath. Because of this property, it can be directly moulded on the patient's body. Before draping is done, the patient's head have to be brought to normal position with the help of another individual or by using Dacron straps made specifically for this purpose.

Fig. Moulding of LTTP material over Patient's body

2. By draping over a POP model.

Another is method is by taking a cast covering the patient's head, neck and upper thorax. The patient's head has to be kept in neutral position. Then the cast is modified properly by providing proper correction. After the final model is obtained. Now hold the mole in a vice horizontally. Cut the HDPE sheet according to model linear and circumferential measurement. Cut two sheets one for anterior shell and one for posterior shell. Put them one after one in the oven. First put posterior one. After melting first one, do the posterior side dripping of model properly. Give the shape at neck region with stockinette and cover the occiput area properly. Whole back side of head should be covered. Now wait to cool the dripped posterior shell. And after it get cooled down then do the anterior part dripping covering chin to T12 level of spine. Anterior shell will overlap posterior shell so do the dripping of anterior shell over the posterior shell. After dripping is done do the trim lines. Cut the trim lines. Mandibular support and occiput support cut out separate from shell. Now the torso shells are ready to assemble with other component. Assembles the other parts with shells that are- turn buckles, metal head frame, mandibular support, pressure pads. This entire component assembles using screws, rivets, straps, press button. Parts, assembly stages and fabrication process is shown in figure given as follows.

Fig. Modification of Positive of POP model

Fabrication Procedure:

Fig. A: Positive POP model, B: Molten HDPE sheet over POP model, C: Draped inside view of posterior shell, D: Outside view of Posterior shell

Assembly of Non- Invasive Pinless Halo Orthosis:

Fig. A: Head ring with occiput and chin support, B: Anterior view, C: Posterior view, D: Lateral view

Features of Non- Invasive Pinless Halo Orthosis: It is non-invasive type of Orthosis. Surgical procedure is not required for its fitment. No pin irritation, pain or any infection is there as pins are absent. Donning and doffing is easy. It gives 80-85% of immobilization. Height of the orthosis is adjustment due to turnbuckles. Required distraction force is applied by turnbuckle just like distraction rods in halo. Anterior and posterior shell gives stability to thoracic spine with normal ventilation. It also provides attachment to turnbuckles and act as foundation of orthosis just like torso vest does in traditional HALO. Pressure pad and occiput support gives required force to control head motion. Hygiene is not a problem. Custom made, cost effective and easy to fabrication. It's easy to wear and less experienced person can also make wore the orthosis to the patient.

Final Design of Non- Invasive Pinless Halo Orthosis:

Fig. A: Ant. View of Orthosis, B: Post. View of Orthosis, C: Right Side View, D: Left Side View of Orthosis

Result:

The newly designed Non-invasive Pinless Halo Orthosis is found to be effective and provides around 80-85% of immobilization. This orthosis can be used as an alternative for the Traditional Halo devices. As this device is simple in design can be fabricated in small setups with readily available materials.

Conclusion:

- Turnbuckles will provide distraction force to cervical spine, just like distraction rod in traditional halo
- They also deloads cervical spine from head load.
- Plastic shells will provide attachment for turnbuckles.
- Pressure pads will provide coupling forces and control motion and maintain head position.
- Metal Face frame and chin support, and anterior turn buckle will control flexion, extension, lateral rotation, lateral bending head and neck.

Discussion:

Spinal disabilities are highly versatile and should be treated at best possible way at its beginning itself. Rehabilitation of Cervical level of disabilities are more crucial and should be managed with more scientific approach. The traditional approach of treating cervical fractures with Halo Devices involves surgical intervention to put the pins inside the skull whereas using the Non Invasive pinless Halo Orthosis can be a great option which avoid postoperative complications as well as easy approach of treatment. With more research and with Statistical analysis, we can derive firm conclusion about this device.

Conflict of Interest: Authors don't have any conflict of interest.

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